

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

The development of procedures and methods to perform analysis on soil and grapes & the development of innovative optical techniques to detect pollution agents on soil and grapes

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY DELIVERABLES D3.1 - D3.2

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the development of procedures and methods to perform advanced analysis based on innovative optical techniques to detect pollutants and/or adulterant agents in water, soil, grapes. More generally they should be transmitted and detectable in the food chain of consumer products. Handy and easy-to-use optical instrumentation is very important for different chemical agents monitoring, is highly relevant for all the safety issues and provides the possibility to assess law and health compliances at each stage of the food chain. As an example, the Surface-enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) method appears highly promising because the intrinsic drawback of Raman spectroscopy, i.e. the natural weakness of the effect and, in turn, of the signal, is overcome thanks to the peculiar interaction between laser light and plasmonic excitations at the SERS substrate. This fact paved the way for the widespread use of SERS sensing not only for food safety but also for biomedicine, pharmaceutical process analysis, forensic science, cultural heritage, and more. However, the current technological maturity of the SERS technique does not find a counterpart in the recognition of SERS as a routine method in compliance protocols. This is mainly due to the very scattered landscape of SERS substrates designed and tailored specifically for the targeted analyte. In fact, a large variety of SERS substrates have been proposed for molecular sensing in different environments and matrices. Advantages and perspectives of SERS sensing in food safety need to be clearly stated and analyzed. Here the focus is limited to specific analytes of interest for producers, consumers and stakeholders in Oltrepò Pavese, addressing the attention to (i) methylene blue in water, (ii) tetracycline, an antibiotic often detected in waste sludges that can be dangerous, for instance, in maize crops, (iii) histamine in a world-famous local product (wine) and (iv) Sudan dyes - used as adulterants - in the production of saffron and other spices, which represent niche crops for Oltrepò [Albini, 2023].

Food contamination describes the event in which a foreign material or substance that can induce foodborne illnesses is introduced into the food material. These events can occur at any step in the food supply chain from producer to consumer during production, processing, distribution, retailing and consumption. Indeed, contamination of raw materials can occur from the soil, sewage, live animals, external surface, and the internal organs of meat animals. Other sources of contamination include water, air, dust, equipment, and employees. Heavy metal contamination in food occurs mainly through pollution of water and soil [Ukaogo, 2020]. According to the European Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 [EU, 2023] (with subsequent amendments (EC) No 1019/2008, Regulation (EU) No 579/2014 and Regulation (EU) 2021/382) the legislator aim is to ensure and verify the food composition and quality with the so-called farm-to-fork approach, i.e., from farms to processing plants and retailers to the final consumer. The key principle is that every subject working in the food chain (and business) must ensure that food is processed free of

contamination from foodborne hazards, at each stage of the production process. This must be achieved through good hygiene practices and procedures based on the hazard analysis and critical control points (HACCP) principles [Motarjemi, 2023]. Among the procedures based on HACCP principles, effective monitoring of food contamination is a key element to ensure the quality of the whole food chain. In the following, we report some interesting case studies useful to highlight the effectiveness of a spectroscopic analytical approach for molecular sensing at different food chain steps. Different SERS strategies used by our research group or by other researchers are presented. In the last part of the document we present and discuss some issues related to the field-use of microbial biosensors.

SERS detection of methylene blue in water

Methylene blue (MB), a common industrial dye, is toxic and it can persist in the environment, representing a pollutant in aquatic environments, with potential risks to human health and ecological systems. It is one of the most abundant pollutants in water, and thus it is important to detect it and remove it from wastewater. Polydopamine (PDA) is a bioinspired polymer widely employed mainly because of its surface adhesive features. In our study we prepared silver nanospheres (AgNPs) by well-known synthetic procedures. Then AgNPs were coated with a thin layer of PDA to exploit the affinity of its surface toward Methylene Blue (MB), and subsequently improve the Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) based MB detection. The details of the different chemical preparations and SERS experimental parameters are reported in Schiavi et al. [Schiavi, 2024].

SERS response of colloidal AgNPs and AgNPs@PDA samples was tested by mixing 990 μL of colloid with 10 μL of the dye solution (with a final concentration of 1 μM) in a cylindrical LDPE vessel. The SERS spectra were collected with a 532 nm laser source, a power density of about 10^3 W cm^{-2} .

To assess the limit of detection of the system, with the same method described above, 990 μL of colloidal sample were mixed with 10 μL of decreasing concentration of MB, exploring a range between 0.025 μM and 5 μM as final concentrations of MB. SERS spectra were collected as previously described.

To test the PDA coated AgNPs on real samples, tap water was spiked with different amounts of MB. Then, to resemble areal application, AgNPs@PDA003 and the spiked water sample were mixed in 1:1 volume ratio. SERS spectra were collected as previously described.

Different optical and morphological properties of AgNPs colloidal suspension were performed. Absorption spectra show the expected LSPR peak centered at 428 nm wavelength (Fig.1). Morphology and size of the obtained nano-objects were characterized by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) showing a mean diameter of $49 \pm 5 \text{ nm}$ and a low polydispersity (Fig. 2). The AgNPs@PDA colloids were further obtained exploiting the self-polymerization of DA with a slight modification of a well-established methodology (Ye, 2017). To study four different possible

thicknesses, 0.03, 0.06, 0.12 and 0.31 mg mL⁻¹ concentration of dopamine were employed, hereafter labelling the synthesized substrates as AgNPs@PDA003, AgNPs@PDA006, AgNPs@PDA012 and AgNPs@PDA031. Before characterization the AgNPs@PDA colloids were washed two times in dd-H₂O.

Figure 1. (a) UV-Visible spectra of bare AgNPs (black) and PDA coated AgNPs obtained with 0.03 (blue), 0.06 (purple), 0.12 (dark green) and 0.31 mg/mL (light green) of dopamine coating; (b) shift of Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance absorption band as a function of dopamine concentration.

Figure 2. Transmission Electron Microscopy images of (a) AgNP@PDA003, (b) AgNPs@PDA006, (c) AgNPs@PDA012 and (d) AgNPs@PDA031 substrates.

To establish the SERS performance of AgNPs@PDA substrates, we proceeded with SERS measurements of MB added at 1.0 μM concentration to the colloidal suspensions of bare AgNPs and AgNPs@PDA samples of different PDA thicknesses. SERS spectra were acquired using a 532 nm laser source. Fig. 3a reports the Raman spectra obtained, and Fig. 3b shows in detail the spectra obtained with AgNPs and AgNPs@PDA003 to easily compare the intensity of the main peak of MB at 1624 cm⁻¹ (assigned to C-C/C-N stretching).

Figure 3. (a) SERS spectra of 1 μM MB solution obtained with silver substrates coated with different thicknesses of PDA: (I) uncoated AgNPs, (II) AgNP@PDA003, (III) AgNP@PDA006, (IV) AgNP@PDA012, (V) AgNP@PDA031; (b) enlargement of SERS spectra of 1 μM MB solution with uncoated AgNPs and AgNP@PDA003.

After having assessed and justified the peculiar affinity between MB and PDA surfaces, we explored the response of AgNP@PDA003 substrate, i.e. the best performing SERS probe, as a function of MB concentration, comparing the obtained signal intensities with those obtained with the uncoated silver substrate. The results are reported in Fig. 4a. As expected, a huge difference is clearly noticeable when comparing the results in the presence and in the absence of a thin PDA layer. The gain in SERS signal is maximized at low concentrations, a fact that clearly reflects the importance of adsorption phenomena due to MB affinity for PDA, with a trend consistent with the well-established formation a monolayer of MB on nanosized PDA surfaces (Fu, 2015).

Indeed, with the PDA coated sample, MB can be detected down to 25 nM (around 10 ppb), while, with the same acquisition conditions, the LOD with bare AgNPs couldn't go below 0.5 μM (around 190 ppb). In addition, the quantitative ability of AgNPs@PDA003 to detect MB was assessed obtaining a linear behavior (Fig. 4b) by plotting the SERS intensities of 1624 cm^{-1} signal against micro-molar concentration of MB (ranging from 0.025 μM to 0.5 μM).

Given these promising results, the usability of AgNP@PDA003 colloid was tested to monitor tap water spiked with different amounts of MB, simulating a real monitoring practice. The experiment was carried out mixing with 1:1 ratio the spiked samples with AgNP@PDA003 colloidal suspension, without any pretreatment; SERS spectra were collected immediately after the mixing and are reported in Fig. 5a.

Figure 4. (a) SERS intensities of 1624 cm^{-1} Raman peak plotted against molar concentration of MB for AgNPs (black dots) and AgNPs@PDA003 substrate (blue dots); (b) SERS spectra obtained using AgNPs@PDA003 substrate in ddH₂O with increasing amounts of MB; (c) Linear regression of 1624 cm^{-1} peak intensities in the linear range of response for AgNPs@PDA003.

Figure 5. (a) SERS spectra obtained using AgNPs@PDA003 in tap water with increasing amount of MB. (b) Linear regression of 1624 cm^{-1} MB peak intensity value in the linear range of response for AgNPs@PDA003.

Fig. 5b shows the intensity of the signal at 1624 cm^{-1} versus the MB concentration in the spiked samples, confirming the linear behavior with a LOD of $0.1\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ (around 40 ppb). It is interesting to notice that in the work of J. Dong et al. [Dong, 2022], MB was detected down to $0.1\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ in lake water samples using a PDA and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) based system. Here PDA was exploited mainly for its reductive properties to synthesize AuNPs, which were further functionalized with a hydro-phobic layer of perfluorodecanthiol, to enrich the analyte close to NPs and prevent its diffusion on the support. Thus, despite the LOD obtained for MB being comparable, here we propose a methodology to obtain a SERS substrate with high sensitivity and reproducibility, but with easier preparation and measurement procedures.

SERS detection of antibiotics in water and soil

The extensive use of antibiotics is an urgent issue nowadays. With an average consumption in Europe of 16.4 daily doses per 1000 inhabitants, to which the consumption for animal healthcare should be added, their presence in the environment is producing high levels of contamination [Barreiro, 2022]. Indeed, the main problem is that human and animal bodies cannot completely metabolize antibiotics. Therefore, a certain quantity is excreted and contaminates urban wastewater and water treatment plants. With a chain effect, these contaminants affect watercourses, lakes, the sea, and soil, if it is fertilized by sewage sludge.

A great additional hazard in antibiotic pollution lies in the fact that the antimicrobial resistance, namely the ability of bacteria to resist the antibiotic effect, has increased [MS,2023]. In this regard, the research carried out at the Department of Clinical-Surgical, Diagnostic and Pediatric Sciences of the University of Pavia [PP,2023] has demonstrated the presence of different antibiotic-resistant bacteria, for instance *Escherichia coli* [AbuAlshaar, 2022], in surface and groundwater of urban and suburban areas of Pavia.

In the following, we report on different SERS approaches to detect Tetracycline (TET). TET is a broad-spectrum antibiotic, widely employed for both human and animal care in view of its high

performance combined with the low cost. Its action is potent against different Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, protozoan parasites, including atypical organisms such as mycoplasma, chlamydia, and rickettsia. A detailed analysis of the tetracycline's issue in the aquatic environment is presented in [EU,2009]. Figure 6 reports TET's molecular structure (C₂₂H₂₄N₂O₈) [TC,2023]. Because of the widespread presence of tetracycline's residues in the environment and especially in the food chain, careful monitoring is needed to control that its concentration is below the Minimum Residual Levels (MRLs) imposed by the EU, namely 0.1 ppm in muscle and milk, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6 ppm in eggs, liver and kidney, respectively [Amangelsin, 2023].

Figure 6. Molecular structure of Tetracycline from [TC,2023].

Its Raman spectrum (see Figure 7) is characterized by an intense Raman activity between 450 and 1750 cm⁻¹. The most intense modes fall around 1300 cm⁻¹ and 1620 cm⁻¹. In [Leybold, 2003] a comparison between the Raman signatures of fully protonated tetracycline in aqueous environment and those of tetracycline hexahydrate in the crystalline state has been presented. The use of tetracycline for animal healthcare can also result in the presence of TET's residuals in livestock products, like for instance milk and eggs [Ghimpeteanu, 2022]. Thus, it is mandatory to verify that the presence of this antibiotic doesn't exceed the MRLs imposed by the EU. In [Marques, 2019], a low-cost SERS sensor based on Ag nanoparticles on a cardboard packaging substrate is used to detect TET spiked in milk with concentration ranging from 0.01 to 1000 ppm. The analysis of the collected Raman spectra on dried drops was performed through a principal component analysis approach, demonstrating a sensitivity of 0.1 ppm. S. Dhakal et al [Dhakal, 2018] performed a SERS investigation making use, also in this case, of Ag nanoparticles, but in a colloidal form.

Figure 7. Raman spectrum of 0.1 M aqueous TET solution (upper panel) collected by using a 785 nm laser source and (lower panel) computed by DFT calculations. Adapted with permission from [Muhammad, 2020]. Copyright 2020 American Chemical Society.

The measurements were performed on both water- and milk-tetracycline solutions on spiked wet drops by means of a portable Raman spectrometer, Raman Explorer 785, Headwall Photonics, Fitchburg, MA, USA, connected through a 100 μm slit to one end of a bifurcated optical fiber. The other end of the fiber was connected to a 785 nm laser module (I0785MM0500MF, Innovative Photonics Solutions, Monmouth Junction, NJ, USA) to deliver the light source for sample excitation. A LOD of 0.01 ppm was demonstrated. More elaborate SERS substrates based on Ag nanostructures are presented in Muhammad et al. [Muhammad, 2020] and in Yang et al. [Yang, 2021]. In particular, the first work presents a transparent substrate composed of highly ordered Ag nanoparticle (NPs) arrays fabricated with a protocol based on the anodic aluminum oxide template-assisted electrochemical deposition plus acid etching and finally sputtering the Ag NPs. This approach allowed them to reach a LOD of 1×10^{-9} M (≈ 0.44 ppb). The second work uses a PDMS substrate. The TET-spiked milk was injected on the PDMS substrate enriched by Ag nanoparticles, then sucked out after 6 min; then the SERS measurements were performed, reaching a detection limit of 0.28 ppb.

SERS detection of histamine in wine

Histamine (His) is a biogenic amine composed of an imidazole ring attached to an ethylamine chain ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$) (see Figure 8 for the molecular structure). This amine is the product of the enzymatic decarboxylation of histidine, which is an amino acid naturally present in several tissues in the human body [Bush, 2003]. The endogenous histamine is mainly stored in mast cells and basophils and its release in the body is promoted by different stimulations. Although His is

involved in many physiological processes as a neurotransmitter [Kovacova,2015], it is mainly known for the diffused intolerance associated with it. Some individuals cannot properly metabolize exogenous histamine. This may cause allergy-like symptoms, such as rash, general effects on the gastrointestinal tract, low blood pressure, and headache.

Figure 8. 2D molecular structure of histamine, reproduced from (PC., 2023).

Indeed, this amine is naturally present in the animals' tissues, plants, and food like foodstuffs that have undergone the fermentation process, such as wine. Indeed, the primary source of wine intolerance lies in the presence of high histamine concentration [Wantke, 1994]. The origin of the occurrence of high or low levels of His in wine is still controversial, although studies have demonstrated that the variation in His level seems independent of the grape variety [Konakovsky, 2011 and Wantke, 2008], while a possible dependence on the production process could be assumed, in particular by selecting a proper bacterial strain [Pérez, 2021].

No limit is currently set by the EU on His content in wine, although the International Organization of Vine and Wine advises the winemakers not to exceed 12 mg/L, roughly 12 ppm [Pérez, 2021].

Figure 9 reports the Raman spectra of histamine dication in solid powder. The high wavenumber region is dominated by the activity related to C-H and N-H stretching modes. An intense Raman activity is also registered between 600 and 1700 cm⁻¹. A detailed assignment of solid His modes as well as of histamine diluted in normal and heavy water can be found in [Collado, 2000] and [Ramírez, 2003] for dihydrochloride and free-base amine, respectively.

Figure 9. Raman spectrum of natural histamine dihydrochloride. Adapted and reproduced with permission from [Collado, 2000].

A wide literature is available on the detection of histamine in food by means of SERS. We restrict our focus on His detection in wine by SERS. However, we also consider works where detection takes place in liquids or simply treat the problem of histamine detection from a general point of view.

Bettini et al. [Bettini, 2019] deals with SERS detection of histamine in wine. An AgNPs-cellulose hybrid substrate is proposed as an easy approach to detect His in liquid. A LOD of about 1×10^{-4} ppb for histamine in water is claimed. The measurements were performed by simply dropping the liquid sample on the substrate and using a bench-top Raman system with a 532 nm laser source. As proof of concept, this cellulose-based device was also tested on real samples: a commercial and a more expensive white wine, stored in tetra pack and glass, respectively. The sensitivity of the sensor was confirmed by means of high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) measurements.

A novel approach for both extracting and sensing histamine in food is proposed in [Wu, 2017] by exploiting the molecular imprinted polymers (MIPs) strategy to improve the selectivity of the substrate itself. Upconversion particles (UCNPs) were covered by a layer of MIP doped with AgNPs. Thus, the UCNPs@MIPs-AgNPs sensor simultaneously enhanced the Raman signal and quenched the fluorescence response. The SERS measurements on His were performed by depositing the UCNPs@MIPs-AgNPs pellet obtained after centrifugation of the colloidal suspension onto a gold-coated microarray chip. Before mixing, the pristine UCNPs@MIPs-AgNPs colloids were spiked with different concentrations of His. The SERS spectra were characterized by the four more intense His modes at 1268 cm^{-1} , 1331 cm^{-1} , 1572 cm^{-1} , and 1427 cm^{-1} . Among them, the one at 1331 cm^{-1} , ascribed together with the ones at 1268 cm^{-1} and 1572 cm^{-1} to the stretching and breathing of the imidazole ring, is reported to be the most dose-sensitive, and allowed to obtain a good calibration curve. A LOD of 0.04 ppm is reported. The reliability of the proposed sensors was tested in real food samples, namely red wine, rice wine, and canned tuna spiked with three different known quantities of histamine (5, 15 and 30 mg/L). The procedure showed a good accordance between the results obtained with UCNPs@MIPs-AgNPs sensors and with HPLC tests.

Yang et al. [Yang, 2022] describe a sensor based on Au NPs combined with carbon dots. They demonstrate that after derivatization of His (D-His), a key passage for His detection, the presence of β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) decorated N,Zn co-doped carbon dots was decisive in the detection of a clear D-His SERS signal. The LOD attainable with the proposed substrate was about $10 \mu\text{M}$ ($\approx 1 \text{ ppm}$). The sensor was also tested on real samples, namely fresh and fermented juices and rice wine, by performing spike and recovery experiments. Once again, the SERS results on His detection were consistent with those obtained by means of HPLC measurements.

A colloidal SERS substrate of Au NPs was proposed in [Kolosova, 2019]. A detailed characterization of the substrate revealed a sensitivity in dihydrochloride His detection down to about 10 ppb (1×10^{-7} M).

Au NPs were also exploited to detect His in a work by Zhu, H et al [Zhu, 2021]. An AuNPs substrate embedded in SiO₂ was synthesized with the aim of achieving the clinical diagnosis of allergic diseases. The SERS measurements were performed both in water and serum, pointing out LODs values of 10⁻⁸ g/L (0.01 ppb) and 10⁻⁶ g/L (1 ppb), respectively. The exotic aspect is that the analysis of His SERS spectrum was performed on the low-frequency region, namely under 200 cm⁻¹. Indeed, for an allergic sample a His mode at 83 cm⁻¹ is possibly observed.

An indirect SERS-tag strategy, specific for His detection, is described by Chen C. et al. [Chen, 2023]. The substrate is made up of magnetic Fe₃O₄@Au-aptamer nanoparticles that represent the histamine recognition probe, and of a complementary DNA (c-DNA) carrying an Ag@4-MBN@Ag system, which is the SERS signal probe. After the incubation of the two parts for a specific time, a core-satellite SERS aptasensor (Ag@4-MBN@Ag-c-DNA/Fe₃O₄@Au-aptamer) is obtained. Under a magnetic field, this SERS aptasensor exhibits a strong SERS signal characteristic of 4-MBN. As the content of His increases and it is bound by the aptamer, the 4-MBN signal decreases since the His-aptamer bound leads to the detachment of the SERS signal probe (containing 4-MBN). With this novel strategy a LOD of 0.65×10^{-3} ng/mL (0.65×10^{-3} ppb) was achieved. The tested samples were obtained by first incubating the sensor with His solution at different concentrations. Then, the obtained product was collected by magnetic separation, washed with a PBS buffer, and redispersed into a PBS buffer solution. The SERS measurements were performed on the final samples dropped on a silica substrate. This procedure was also used to perform measurements on spiked beer, obtaining good recovery values. Finally, the sensitivity of the sensor was tested on real samples, i.e. shoyu, rice vinegar, kirschwasser, and fish samples. The detected His levels were compared with HPCL results, and no significant differences were observed.

SERS detection of Sudan as an adulterant of saffron

Sudan I-IV are a class of azo dyes, which are fat-soluble compounds mostly used as plastic colorants. The detection of saffron (*Crocus Sativus*) adulteration with Sudan is an interesting subject for the scientific community as Sudan dyes are forbidden in food trading [Kumari, 2021] by the authorities of many countries, including the European Union [EU, 2023b], because of potential danger for human health. The EU has set an MRL for Sudan dyes in food at 0.5 ppm (Commission Directive 2006/33/EC). Any food or food ingredients found to contain more than the established limit should be withdrawn from the market in the EU, and any food containing the synthetic dyes Sudan I-IV, then, may not be placed on the market [BfR, 2023].

Besides saffron, Sudan is used as an adulterant in other powder spices such as chili powder, curry, and paprika. Typically, Sudan dyes as adulterants are in the low ppm concentration range.

Sudan dyes I-IV have similar chemical structures. They are aromatic compounds containing an azo group (-N=N-). The structures of Sudan I-IV are illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Molecular structures of Sudan I-IV, reproduced from [Alomar,2022].

In a study by Ou et al. [Ou, 2017], SERS experiments were carried out using Au-Ag core-shell colloidal nanospheres (Au@Ag) as a substrate. The method was applied in the analysis of standard solutions of Sudan I-IV and Sudan dyes extracted from spiked chili peppers. The LOD for Sudan I and II were 0.10 mg/L, for Sudan III was 0.08 mg/L, and for Sudan IV was 0.2 mg/L. In chili flakes, the LDC was 1 ppm for Sudan I, II, and III and 2 ppm for Sudan IV. These figures of merit are approximately ten times larger than those for standard solutions due to the interference of non-target molecules in the samples.

Detection of methanol-extracted hydrophobic Sudan III in real food with sensitivity up to 9 mmol/L was accomplished by using hydrophobic surface-modified silver nanoparticles (lipophilic sensor layers). The combination of SERS with microfluidics significantly reduced the low-reproducibility problem by allowing high data acquisition rates and, consequently, enhanced statistical stability of the dataset.

The ability of SERS to quantify Sudan I-IV dyes was investigated in a recent study by Alomar et al. [Alomar, 2022]. SERS spectra were acquired using a benchtop Raman instrument and gold nanoparticles were employed as the SERS substrate. The authors demonstrated the feasibility of rapidly and simultaneously quantifying all four Sudan dyes in mixtures containing multiple Sudan dyes at different concentrations, with limits of detection of about 10^{-6} mol/L (\approx 0.4 ppm). Stock solutions of the Sudan dyes were diluted in a mixture of water and Acetonitrile (1:10 v/v). Principal component analysis on the SERS spectra made it possible to distinguish and classify the Sudan dyes. Sudan II, III, and IV are structurally derived from Sudan I (1-phenyl-azo-2-naphthol). Nonetheless, the SERS spectra acquired from the different Sudan dyes are markedly different

(Figure 11). This is possibly due to the association of different parts of these molecules with the gold nanoparticles. The interaction between the negatively charged surface of the citrate-capped nanoparticles and the diazene functional group of the sample molecules (the $-N=N-$ can become positively charged) is likely to play an important role. Moreover, ordinary Raman spectra of Sudan dyes (see e.g. Ou, 2017) are strongly modified by the interaction with the SERS substrate. This last effect is ubiquitous in Raman and SERS spectroscopy.

Figure 11. (from [Alomar, 2022]) Representative SERS spectra of Sudan I, II, III, and IV in the concentration ranging between 25 and 50 mM (roughly 7.5 and 15×10^{-3} ppm), matrix - that is the aggregated citrate-capped gold nanoparticles - and the acetonitrile solvent (ACN).

Preliminary SERS investigations on Sudan dyes have recently been performed in our laboratory. Figure 12 reports the SERS spectrum of 5×10^{-7} mol/L (≈ 0.2 ppb) Sudan III collected by means of a Horiba Xplora Raman micro-spectrometer (laser source wavelength of 638 nm). The substrate is an Ag-nanoplate chip. The measurements were performed on solid chips immersed in a solution of Sudan dissolved in acetonitrile, and then dried.

Two prominent lines are observed at about 1130 and 1590 cm^{-1} . According to mode assignments reported in Ou et al. [Ou, 2017] the line at 1130 cm^{-1} can be assigned to C-H in-plane bending, O-H in-plane bending, C-H scissoring in benzene rings, and C-H stretching, whereas the line at 1590 cm^{-1} can be assigned to C-C scissoring in benzene rings, and N=N stretching.

Figure 12. SERS spectrum of 0.2 ppb Sudan III.

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Investigating the field-use of microbial biosensors

The developed biosensor technology is based on living materials including an engineered microbe (living component) embedded in a hydrogel (abiotic component). The microbe includes new DNA-encoded synthetic circuits able to sense the target molecule and respond with the production of a fluorescent molecule or the development of pigmentation. Microbes and hydrogel are mixed and used to fabricate sensing materials (1 x 1 x 0.2 cm or 2 x 2 x 0.2 patches, see Figure 1b) by a 3D bioprinting platform, thus providing a simple, accessible, automatable, and low-cost technique to construct a number of sensors. The Spoke 6 activities include the development of biosensing kits for laboratory-confined use, able to detect organic acids or inorganic molecules in agro-industrial samples to monitor different processes in the FORMIDABILAE flagship project.

Figure 1b: Fabrication workflow for sensing materials. Bioprinted patches are shown on the right as examples

For the VINO flagship project, these sensors should be able to work in the field (i.e., non-confined use), requiring proper containment measures to prevent genetically modified microbe (GMM) escape from the materials. We tested different strategies, based on genetic and physical biocontainment.

The main requirements of such biocontainment strategies are:

- Prevent bacterial escape
- Allow the diffusion of target molecules
- Easy and low-cost fabrication
- User-friendly measurements

Biocontainment strategies

Genetic biocontainment was tested by inserting a programmed cell lysis plasmid into the biosensor strain included in the materials. Lysis could be triggered by adding 3-oxo-C6 homoserine lactone to the surrounding medium to test the on-demand cell death of the escaper cells.

Physical biocontainment was first tested by a thermo-welded 0.2- μm PES membrane acting as an envelope for the living materials.

A second strategy of physical containment was tested by a PDMS box that hosts the living material and a 0.2- μm PES filter used to close the container.

Experimental tests were performed in which the living material was placed into a beaker with water or LB growth medium, and the liquid was analyzed after an overnight incubation to quantify the escapers. Data are provided in Figure 2b. Genetic biocontainment showed a poor performance. The PES envelope showed a better efficiency but a high variability, probably due to changes of the welding efficiency. Even though the PES envelope was promising, it was not considered as a user-friendly strategy as the quantification of biosensor output required the disassembly of the envelope. The PDMS+PES box was the only strategy that reproducibly achieve zero escaper cells in biocontainment assays. In the two physical containment strategies, molecule diffusion across the PES membrane was assessed by qualitatively evaluating the sensor activation.

Figure 2b. Comparison among biocontainment strategies.

An efficient biocontainment with low-cost fabrication techniques was obtained for living biosensors. However, due to the current regulatory restrictions in the EU on GMM release in the environment, this strategy is not immediately applicable for field testing. This was confirmed by a panel of reviewers who rejected a PoC proposal named SMARTWORK-ELM because of the impossibility to carry out field testing with this technology according to the current EU regulations. As this technology guarantees zero escaper GMMs it is likely that it will be usable

when regulations will be modified in the future, however, for now, in the VINO flagship the development of sensors for detecting contaminants in the field with this technique has not been pursued.

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